

FABRICATION OF ORDERED POROUS POLYMER FILM IN CELLULOSE TRIACETATE-MULTIWALLED CARBON NANOTUBE COMPOSITES

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Keywords: *Ordered porous film; cellulose triacetate; multiwalled carbon nanotubes*

1. Introduction

Possessing unique structures and properties, carbon nanotubes (CNTs) are attractive building blocks for novel materials and devices of important practical interest [1]. However, the insolubility or poor dispersibility of pristine CNTs in common solvents poses a serious obstacle to their further development. Various attempts have been made to obtain homogeneous CNT dispersions in both aqueous and organic media [2,3].

Cellulose and its derivatives are major biomolecules and are among the most widely employed natural polymers in industries, such as textiles, packaging materials, films, membranes, and thermoplastics. The potential of cellulose esters has been investigated to confirm cellulose esters as potential biodegradable polymers. Cellulose esters have been used in optical film applications for many decades due to their inherent clarity. Cellulose triacetate (CTA), cellulose diacetate (CD), and certain mixed cellulose esters are utilized for the most important photographic film supports [4].

In this paper, the fabrications of regularly ordered structure in the CTA and CTA-MWNT composite films are reported. The composites were prepared by the dispersion of pretreated MWNTs into the CTA solution in chloroform with varying amounts of MWNT (10, 20, and 30 w/w%). Highly ordered polymer films are produced by evaporating a solution of polymer dissolved in a volatile solvent under humid conditions.

2. Experimentals

2.1 Materials

All the reagents, including CTA (pellets), chloroform ($\geq 99.8\%$), and MWNTs (diameter = 110-170 nm, length = 5-9 nm) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich Co. and used without further treatment with the exception of MWNTs.

2.2 Preparation of composites

About 10 mg of CTA was initially taken in a beaker along with 10 mL of CHCl_3 ; this was stirred for about 1 h to dissolve the CTA completely in CHCl_3 . For the composite films, 10 w/w% of treated MWNTs was added into the CHCl_3 solution containing CTA with continuous stirring for 1 h to obtain a homogeneous mixture. The same procedure was repeated for the 20 and 30 w/w% of MWNTs. For comparison, a patterned film by CTA alone was also obtained without adding the MWNTs. On the other hand, obtaining CNT dispersions by using high concentrations of surfactants or polymers may bring about inconveniences in their further processing, such as producing composite materials. Therefore, an effective non-covalent side wall functionalization technique for working with MWNTs is highly desirable from the viewpoints of both fundamental studies and technical applications.

In this paper, the CTA-MWNT composites with various weight percentages of MWNTs (10, 20, and 30 w/w%) in CTA are abbreviated as CMT-10, CMT-20 and CMT-30, respectively.

2.3 Fabrication of ordered structures in the CMT composites

Fig. 1 shows the schematic diagram of the process of obtaining the patterned structures in the CMT composites. In this process, the chloroform solution containing both CTA and MWNT were mixed to form a grey-colored solution. The solution was sonicated for about 2 h to obtain a uniform dispersion. The obtained dispersion was carefully transferred to a Petri dish containing small circular discs with a diameter of 1 cm. The solvent was evaporated under humid conditions to form thin films containing ordered structures. The small circular discs acted as substrates holding the CMT composite films. A solution of 1.0 mg/mL of the composite in chloroform was cast on a circular glass

disc. For a highly ordered patterned structure, evaporated water was applied on the solution surface through an air pump with a flow rate of 0.5 L/min at a temperature of 25 °C and relative humidity of 60 ± 2 %.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Honeycomb patterns in the CTA and CMT composite films

Fig. 2 shows the typical patterns of porous polymer film investigated by SEM at 10 μm magnification in the CTA and the CMT composites. The images show somewhat ordered structures regardless of the added MWNT concentration (Figs. 2(a) for CTA, 2(b) for CMT-10, 2(c) for CMT-20, and 2(d) for CMT-30), although differences have been observed in the pore structure such as pore size distribution, wall thickness, and inside structure of pore hole. Among the films, the film pattern obtained in the CTA alone was well ordered with large wall thickness (Fig. 2(a)). The patterns obtained in the CMT composites demonstrated an ordered structure with a web-like, non-uniform pore size. The wall thickness between pores decreased in the composite films where high amounts of MWNTs were added (Figs. 2(c) and (d)). This indicates that the ordered pattern in the CMT composites films is mainly organized by the composition of CTA in the composites. Then, this result means that patterned films can also be fabricated by similar composite systems obtained by the dispersion of other inorganic materials into the CTA solution, which acts as an organizing backbone for the patterned films.

Fig.1. Schematic diagram showing the formation of the ordered structures through the dispersion of MWNT in the CTA solution

Fig. 2. Typical patterns investigated by SEM in the CTA film and the CTA-MWNT composite films under the physical conditions of 20 °C and a relative humidity of 60% with an air flow rate of 0.5 mL/min (a) for CTA, (b) for CMT-10, (c) for CMT-20, and (d) for CMT-30

4. References

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